

MAIN PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY

Muhitdinova Dildora Alisher qizi

A junior employee of the Research Institute "Mahalla and Family"

Egamberdiyeva Nodira Melibayevna

Director of Research Institute "Mahalla and Family"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12602891>

Abstract: This article focuses on gender mainstreaming and gender itself. It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of expression and the concepts of gender and sex we will dwell in detail on the main principles of provision.

Key words: Gender, gender, biological, social, gender stability, identity.

Gender is a social aspect of relations between men and women that is manifested in all spheres of society's life and activities, including politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education and science. The concept of gender equality means equal rights and opportunities of women and men in all spheres of society's life and activities, including politics, economy, law, culture, education, science, and sports. The main principles of ensuring gender equality:

- Legality;
- Democracy;
- Openness;
- Transparency.

It is known that the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" adopted on September 2, 2019 was approved as a legal protection and legal guarantee aimed at the place of women in society¹

The good thing is that since thousands of years, inequality between men and women in society and the issue of solving it have always been relevant. In particular, as stated in Article 1 of the law, the purpose of the law is to regulate relations in the field of equal rights and opportunities for women and men.

It is true that the era we are living in, while the reforms of the reforming Uzbekistan are focused on the primacy of human interests, still a very large number of family disputes are cases of non-recognition of women's rights by men, as well as in some cases, women's rights and opportunities are not sufficiently important in society. it is true that it is not given.

Against such negative situations, in Article 2 of this law, "Legislative documents on guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men consist of this Law and other legal documents.

If the international agreement of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates different provisions than those stipulated in the legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men, the provisions of the international agreement shall be applied.

Also, the law mentions the concept of gender, according to which gender is the relationship between women and men in all spheres of social life and activity, including

¹ <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/yangilanayotgan-ozbekistonda-gender-tenglikning-huquqiy-asoslari>

politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education. and the social aspect manifested in the fields of science is shown. Therefore, the concept of gender does not represent only the interests of women. Perhaps the fact that representatives of both sexes are boldly walking towards their dreams and goals suggests that they should be given the same opportunity to improve the quality of life. One of the requirements of a developed society is the provision of equal rights for men and women.

In fact, ancient Greek scholars such as Socrates, Aristotle, and Plato considered the polis, where equality and justice prevailed in society, as the best state. as the best laws, they put forward the laws that guarantee the equality of all. The idea of equality between men and women was used by the Greek scientist Antiphon in his works, who stated: "Nature creates everyone: women and men equal, but people develop laws that make people unequal." One of the scientists, Abu Nasr Farabi, in his book "The City of Virtuous People" noted that a country where equality reigned as a country striving for virtue, while in 1791, the declaration of citizenship and women's rights prepared by Olympia De Gouge stated that women have the right to think freely and express their opinions for the first time. acknowledged. If we pay attention to the legal development of gender equality, first of all, it is permissible to analyze the historical-theoretical and legal aspects of the legal foundations of gender equality, international and national legislation.

Institutional and personnel conditions ensure overcoming the problems of gender equality. The formation of institutional conditions depends on global, national and local policies to implement the principles of gender equality. This study shows how the formation of institutional conditions through national policy can be ensured on the example of the proposed methodology of concept implementation. Despite a favorable political environment, a number of social and institutional barriers continue to prevent girls and young women from pursuing higher education in the security and defense sector, as well as ensuring the same level of success as men in the learning process. The prioritization of science and technology in security and defense education policy may contribute to the further exclusion of female students unless additional measures are taken to promote women's participation in these areas. Addressing gender equality in the education system with a focus on improving girls' learning outcomes and outcomes is crucial to achieving the goals of women's protection in the country.

The security needs of women and men need to be taken into account, often addressing their different perspectives, stereotypes and prejudices. This is achieved through equal participation of both men and women in decision-making processes, in the formation and implementation of policies based on mutual enrichment of knowledge about gender equality and their differences. An important element of this approach is the creation of conditions that lead to an increase in the number of women in security and defense facilities. Increasing the number of women in public research institutions allows enriching the formulation of security and defense policy with new experience, knowledge, interests and needs of both women and men. In this way, institutions will be more effective in responding to different security needs. Integrating the principles of gender equality can change the perception of the military as an institution, which is mainly engaged in violence and hostilities, in a system aimed at building peace and security. However, for this to happen, security sector reform processes must take into account the gender dimension both in terms of rules and procedures and in terms of organizational culture.

First of all, I will touch on the role of the family institution in ensuring gender equality let's go, It's no secret that the family plays the most important role in the education of a person, child he is born in a family, grows up, his ideas about the world are formed in him, initial learns moral rules. Human feelings are nurtured in the family, world, views on the place of people appear in it. In the same period gender stereotypes also begin to form in the child's mind. These stereotypes how to dress the child according to his gender, how to style his hair, in the child's early infancy, such as giving a car or a doll the decisions and actions of adults matter. Own in turn, the presence of such gender stereotypes in the human mind and reflected in their behavior is supported by the senior representatives of the society and family. Boy imitating cooking or cars A girl who is interested in drawing may be reprimanded by adults. Because gender stereotypes have a deep place in the social consciousness.

When the first attitudes related to gender begin to form in the family environment, social environment, especially the child lives in their strengthening the place of the neighborhood will be big. It is not for nothing that "one child has seven neighborhood parents" such proverbs were not created in our nation. In the words of the President, "The neighborhood is our nation, preserving our national customs and traditions for centuries a cradle of goodness and education, a place of good neighborliness and harmony. We neighborhood, which is rare in the world, combines a person with society A state with the people, which teaches to live together and educates in the spirit of tolerance we understand a unique structure that acts as a reliable bridge between²

Family and neighborhood in the issue of inculcating gender equality in young people. In addition to institutions, the educational system is also very important. Because what is in the child views about what is right and what is wrong preschool education institution, school and later through a higher education institution is formed. The most important indicator in this is the organization of the education system related to maturity. That is, education in our country is secular, boys and girls study together in the form of classes. At school, boys and girls are opposite sexes who are not family members for the first time spends a lot of time with representatives. It's girls and boys in the class the existence of a properly established system of relations between young people it is the basis for the formation of a correct worldview in relation to gender.

This study proposes a methodology for implementing the principles of gender equality in the educational process of training for the security and defense sector. The methodology includes the following main components: 1. Identification of gender stereotypes in the educational institution that cause problems of gender equality (language problems, in assessing performance, access to teachers and educational resources). 2. Expansion of the curriculum and creation of new gender courses based on the methodology of teaching gender issues and integration of elements into different courses. Gender mainstreaming in the curricula of higher education institutions in the security sector is one of the components of the methodology for implementing the concept of gender equality. 3. Development of a network of gender advisers for the methodological and scientific direction of the policy of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the educational process of educational institutions

² <http://uza.uz/posts/250751>

in the security sector. 4. Development of competence of all subjects of educational environment (expert, methodical and social)

References:

1. Introduction to Gender Relations Theory and Practice. -T. "Uzbekistan", 2007.
2. Outline of the Basics of Gender Studies course. -T. "Uzbekistan". 2003.
3. BADOO, C. Internationalisation and the Challenges of Gender Equality in Higher Education. In Internationalisation of African Higher Education, 2013, p. 33-52. Sense Publishers, Rotterdam